
Social Media Addiction and Its Impact on the Parent-Child and Romantic Relationships

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Abstract: *Social Media is perceived as the beacon of communication change. Social Media is a product of New Media technology which encompasses varied forms like media sharing and networking platforms; content creation and publishing tools. Social Media platforms have tremendous power to do good as well to pose threat to its potential users. Social Media is not only inescapable but very much within the reach of the masses and what makes its users depend on it is its 'accessibility' and 'data portability'. The dependency of users on Social Media makes it very addictive and poses greater threats to the functioning of human relationships. This paper reviews the literature for investigating the impact of 'Social Media Addiction' on the parent-child relationships and romantic relationships. The review of literature in general focuses on the meaning of concepts like Internet, Social Media, Addiction, and Internet Addiction and in specific focuses on the Social Media Addiction. The review of Social Media Addiction is categorized in two themes: 'Impact of Social Media Addiction on the Parent-Child Relationships' and 'Impact of Social Media Addiction on the Romantic Relationships'. In Discussion part the emphasis is laid on the inferences drawn from the review of literature. In a positive attempt to reduce dependency on the Social Media, the present review paper proposes constructive solutions to prevent and overcome Social Media Addiction for building healthy social relationships.*

Keywords: *Internet, Internet Addiction, Social Media, Social Networking Sites, Social Media Addiction, Parent-Child Relationship, Romantic Relationship*

1. INTRODUCTION

Social implications of the Internet and Social Media are a recurrent subject prevailing in the Sociology of Internet. Many utopian claims and dystopian cautions based on the extrapolations derived from technological notions - possibilities and fears of technology' have paved way for the better understanding of Internet and Social Media (DiMaggio et al., 2001, pp. 307-308). These claims and warnings have further delineated how Internet and Social Media usage have become inseparable aspects in the lives of human beings because they are impacting the existing patterns of social behaviour by positively or negatively affecting the human relationships (see Rheingold, 2000; Nie & Hillygus, 2002; Farrugia, 2013).

It is important to understand that Social Media is a very broad term and Social Networking Sites are one of the popular forms of Social Media (Kaplan & Haenlein, 2010). The addictive nature and unbridled popularity of the Social Networking Sites have given them an upper hand over the other forms of Social Media.

With the intrusion of Smartphones in the public sphere, many social media platforms have become much more accessible than before. Users are not required to pay for making a profile on the social media platforms like Facebook, WhatsApp, YouTube, Instagram, Twitter or Snapchat and these social media platforms are readily available on almost every Smartphone in the form of applications which consume less mobile data. Today, one need not log-in to one's laptop or desktop for using Social Media as Social Media applications can be easily accessed through Smartphones; this accessibility also implies that one can freely use Social Media while travelling or at any place outside one's home. Thus, Social Media is not only easily accessible but also characterized by data portability and mobility because Smartphones can be carried anywhere without worrying about excessive space. The data portability of Social Media through Smartphones is making its users more dependent on it and the unchecked usage of Social Media by the users is making them more addicted to it (Jeong et al., 2016; Amankwaa & Blay, 2018; Sarwar & Soomro, 2013). The massive usage of Social Media has triggered a debate among the researchers on the pros and cons of Social Media pertaining to its impact on the human relationships. Some researchers substantiate Social Media as a powerful tool for strengthening human relationships, bridging and bonding social capital (Vallor, 2012;

Ahn, 2012; Kanter, Afifi & Robbins, 2012) while others substantiate Social Media as a debilitating tool for harming and breaking relationships (Phillips, 2009; Abbasi & Alghamdi, 2017).

The ineludible nature of Social Media has kept the users hooked to its addictive social networking platforms. Thus, it is imperative for us to study the impact of Social Media like Social Networking Sites on the human relationships.

Before proceeding to the review of literature it is important to have a look at the research method and objectives.

2. RESEARCH METHOD

For formulation of the research objectives relevant sources of literature have been reviewed which included books, newspaper articles, magazines, research papers from journals and the published theses. Firstly, empirical studies and conceptual papers have been identified for initiating investigation of the research issues pertaining to the concepts like Internet, Social Media, Internet Addiction and Social Media Addiction. Secondly, the inclusion of relevant sources of literature was done with an aim to examine the impact of Social Media Addiction on the human relationships. As human relationships cover a very broad range of relationships, difficult to operationalize, a careful screening of the identified empirical studies was done with a specific inclusion criterion which focussed only on two specific units of relationships: parent-child relationships and romantic relationships. This inclusion criterion became a prerequisite for ensuring that studies included for the present review primarily focused on the 'impact of social media addiction on the parent-child relationships and romantic relationships'.

3. OBJECTIVES

- i. To examine the impact of Social Media Addiction on the parent-child relationships
- ii. To examine the impact of Social Media Addiction on the romantic relationships

4. REVIEW OF LITERATURE

Relevant sources of literature have been reviewed with a general focus on the meaning of concepts like Internet, Social Media, Addiction, Internet Addiction, and with a specific focus on the Social Media Addiction and its impact on the human relationships. The present review takes into consideration only one form of Social Media, i.e. social networking sites because they are the popular forms of Social Media which most potently impact the human relationships. Since, 'human relationships' entail panoptic relationships which aren't easy to operationalize, an effort has been made to examine the impact of Social Media Addiction on two specific units of relationships: parent-child relationships and romantic relationships. It is important to understand that 'romantic relationships' cover those relationships which have *romance* as a key functional factor like in dating relationships, intimate friendships, live-in relationships and married relationships. The present review of Social Media Addiction is categorized in two themes: 'Impact of Social Media Addiction on the Parent-Child Relationships' and 'Impact of Social Media Addiction on the Romantic Relationships'.

4.1 Internet – Meaning of the word Internet

Internet is all pervasive. Many e-commerce companies like Amazon, and Flipkart are heavily dependent on the Internet. Internet is a basic prerequisite for the functioning of Social Media platforms. Lives of human beings all around the globe took a startling turn with the arrival of Internet, which makes the topic of the 'Invention and origin of Internet' quite interesting. Internet brought a '*Change*', a social change which cannot be rewound. In the contemporary era it has changed the way people work and communicate. The way Internet rose to popularity stands unparalleled to any other form of media. The popularity graph of Internet and its offshoots like Social Networking Sites is such that even Television and Radio programs are being promoted currently via Social Networking Sites. Kerschbaumer (2001) stated that while Radio took over thirty years to reach 50 million users, the Internet has captivated the same size audience in less than five years.

'Internet' refers to "*electronic networks of networks that links people and information through computers and other digital devices facilitating person to person communication and information retrieval*" (DiMaggio et al., 2001: 307).

4.2 Internet as New Media

Narayana and Malloli (2013: 3) state that New Media devices are very much popular and their usage has significantly increased. The New Media devices comprise of "Internet, mobile phones, e-mail, computer, laptop, tablets, iPad, social networks, blogs, multimedia, integrated media like radio, TV and Internet and mobile phones, video phone, wireless communication devices from phone to Internet and all satellite based and cable communication devices". They further write, "The nerve centre of New Media basically is the integration of Internet, telecommunications and satellite communication". Social Media platforms are the product of New media technology.

4.3 Internet Usage: Computer Mediated Communication and Human Relationships

In the present century, many social thinkers have developed their interest in Internet as a medium to develop and maintain social relationships (Haythornthwaite & Wellman, 2002). In present day techno-savvy societies, the lives of people are constructed by communication, mainly the Internet, which has changed lives, while the Social Networking Sites are also creating an impact on the behavior of people and relationships. Due to the union of 'post-industrialization with globalization', each new form of technology, be it mobile phones or the Internet, acts as a prognosis to intensify the experience of globalization (Castells, 1998).

Research studies highlight that the Internet users primarily make use of Internet for establishing social affiliations and promoting communication with fellow users; studies report the formation of new relationships among the users of computer-mediated communication (Parks & Floyd, 1996; McKenna, Green & Gleason, 2002).

4.4 Social Media – Definition and Meaning

If Web 2.0 constitutes the technological and ideological base, User Generated Content (UGC) can be referred as "a sum of all the ways in which people make use of Social Media" (Kaplan & Haenlein, 2010: 61).

Social Media is "a group of Internet based applications that build on the ideological and technological foundations of Web 2.0, and that allow the creation and exchange of user generated content" (Kaplan & Haenlein, 2010: 61). The social aspect of the term "implies that it exists in a social space" (Rodriguez, 2011: 539), which may be used for individual, professional or entertainment purposes, and social networks cultivated by individuals. The media component of the term implies that it is through digital devices, digital networks and social networks that the social interactions are mediated. It can't be denied that the demarcation boundaries are blurred between social media and Web 2.0 tools - "web apps". Social media encompasses varied number of technological platforms marked by community and collaboration. It is not easy to describe Social Media citing one definition (Kaplan & Haenlein, 2010), but by examples it becomes easy to describe social media. Social media comprises of multimedia platforms, online applications, virtual games and social worlds, wikis, blogs and social networking sites (McEwan, 2012).

4.5 Forms of Social Media

Social media comprise of "(a) social networking sites, such as Facebook, Twitter, and LinkedIn, (b) media sharing sites, such as YouTube and Flickr, (c) creation and publishing tools, such as wikis and blogs, (d) aggregation and republishing through RSS feeds, and (e) remixing of content and republishing tools" (Greenhow, 2011:140).

Social Networking Sites and media sharing sites are the most popular and widely used forms of Social Media.

It is not possible to understand Internet Addiction and Social Media Addiction without making reference to the Addiction and its forms. So, it is imperative for us to understand the basic meaning of Addiction.

4.6 Addiction – Definition and Meaning of Addiction

Addiction refers to an individual's dependency on a substance or an activity marked by compulsive indulgence for using a substance or compulsive indulgence for excessive and repeated engagement in an activity to an extent that it harms the well-being of an individual. In simple words addiction of a substance or an activity not only makes an individual dependent on it but also brings significant changes in the behavior of an individual. Addiction is accompanied with problems in fulfilling one's duties and it also affects personal, familial and societal relationships (see Carson et al. 2007).

According to Carson et al. (2007, p.412), “*Addictive behavior is behavior based on the pathological need for a substance or activity – may involve the abuse of substances such as nicotine, alcohol, or cocaine.*”

Centre for Addiction and Mental Health, Canada (2012) describes addiction with the help of 4 Cs (cited in Aanchal, S., 2018, p. 34):

- 1.) Craving;
- 2.) Loss of control of amount or frequency of use;
- 3.) Compulsion to use;
- 4.) Use despite consequences

4.6.1 Forms of Addiction

According to Hollander and Allen (2006, p. 1670), addiction can be categorized as 1) *behavioral addiction* and 2) *substance addiction* and there is consideration to create a separate diagnostic category which combines behavioral and substance addiction. Examples of Behavioral addiction are: Internet Addiction, Compulsive Buying Disorder, pathological gambling, kleptomania, and compulsive sexual behavior (Cited in Aanchal, S., 2018, p. 35). Substance addiction is referred to dependency on drugs irrespective of the form of drugs like nicotine, heroin, cocaine, barbiturates, cannabis, opium or dependency on alcohol.

It is important at this point to understand behavioral addiction before examining Internet Addiction and Social Media Addiction.

In simple language Behavioral Addiction can be summarized with the help of following stages:

1. Engagement of an individual in an activity primarily for deriving pleasure, for example, surfing Internet, using Social Media, playing video games, online shopping, gambling, watching pornographic material and sex .
2. Activity becomes a habit and leads to continuous indulgence in the activity
3. Continuous Indulgence in the activity causes Compulsive Behavior/Compulsive Usage
4. Compulsive Behavior negatively affects the well being of an individual by disrupting routine activities and life balance. This compulsive behavior poses harm to the state of mind of an individual and further negatively affects the individual’s personal and familial relationships, work place activities, household chores and so on.

4.7 Internet Addiction

Internet Addiction refers to an Internet user’s dependency on internet marked by excessive usage of Internet in a way that a user loses control over Internet activity by experiencing extreme difficulty in controlling one’s usage; this behavior of uncontrolled Internet usage often leads to deterioration of an individual’s well being.

Block (2008, p. 306) states that Internet addiction can be summarized in four components:

excessive use, often associated with a loss of sense of time or a neglect of basic drives, (2) *withdrawal*, including feelings of anger, tension, and/or depression when the computer is inaccessible, (3) *tolerance*, including the need for better computer equipment, more software, or more hours of use, and (4) *negative repercussions*, including arguments, lying, poor achievement, social isolation, and fatigue (para.1).

Young (1998) in her study found that users who were dependents on Internet experienced problems at their workplace and in dealing with personal or familial relationships. Internet dependents were unable to control or moderate their Internet usage. Parent-Child Relationships, dating relationships and marriage lives were found to be badly affected by this Internet dependency. The study compared the condition of Internet dependents to alcoholics and compulsive gamblers who irrespective of their excessive ‘occupational, financial and relationship’ problems find it difficult to stop drinking or betting.

Lin and Tsai (2002) in their study conducted on high school adolescents found that adolescents who were addicted to Internet formed the habit of compulsively indulging in the activity of Internet usage. When these adolescents

tried controlling their usage they experienced withdrawal symptoms which made it difficult for them to control their Internet usage signifying their addiction to the Internet. The findings of this study revealed that just like any other form of addiction, Internet too negatively affects the health, academics and parent-child relationships of the adolescents who were addicted to it.

Nie and Hillygus (2002) in their study found that substantive amount of time spent on Internet comes from time spent on discretionary activities like videogames, music, reading, television watching, social activities and hobbies rather than non-discretionary activities like pay work, housework, childcare and sleeping.

4.8 Social Media Addiction

'Social Media Addiction' is inextricably linked with 'Internet Addiction' (IA) because it is through Internet that we have an access to Social Media. It would not be wrong to state that 'Social Media Addiction' is the latest form of 'Internet Addiction'. Thus, we can conclude that Social Media Addiction just like Internet Addiction is a form of behavioral addiction.

According to Griffiths (2013, p. 1):

Just like substance related addictions, it would appear that in some individuals, SNS addiction incorporates the experience of the 'classic' addiction symptoms, namely mood modification (i.e., engagement in SNSs leads to a favorable change in emotional states), salience (i.e., behavioral, cognitive, and emotional preoccupation with the SNS usage), tolerance (i.e., ever increasing use of SNSs over time), withdrawal symptoms (i.e., experiencing unpleasant physical and emotional symptoms when SNS use is restricted or stopped), conflict (i.e., interpersonal and intrapsychic problems ensue because of SNS usage), and relapse (i.e., addicts quickly revert back to their excessive SNS usage after an abstinence period).

Status of Mind report (2017, p. 3) revealed that users of Social Media reported Social Media as more addictive in nature than addictive substances like cigarettes and alcohol; the report also substantiated that due to excessive and uncontrolled Social Media usage mental health problems like anxiety and depression rose by 70% in the previous 25 years further affecting the well being of people.

Figure 1: 'Social Media Addiction' by Colin Behrens (2017). Retrieved from Pixabay. [Copyright Free Image – free for commercial use, and no attribution required].

See Figure 1. Image designed by Behrens, C. (2017) is a creative representation of Social Media Addiction. One can observe the icons of Social Media Sites designed on the capsules indicating that just like *addictive drugs* these Social Media sites work as an *addictive daily pill* for the Social Media users who are literally dependent on them. Another interesting thing to observe is that the pills are named 'Social Media' on the pill carton box and dosage description is

50 MB of mobile data per pill. Social Media is more accessible than before with some 4G Network companies offering users 1.5 GB mobile data for daily usage as a part of their mobile data pack plans.

Al-Menayes (2015) in a study found a positive correlation between time spent on Social Media and factors of Social Media addiction. The study substantiated that the more amount of time spent by the users on Social Media leads to a significant increase in the exhibition of social media addiction symptoms among the users (*users here refer to individuals who use Social Media). The results further revealed that the users who reported satisfaction with the functions of social media were more likely to be addicted to Social Media (see, p. 26).

4.9 Impact of Social Media Addiction on the Parent-Child Relationships

It is very important for parents and children to have face-to-face communication with each other but this can only happen if the parents and children both take out quality time for each other rather than wasting time on Smartphones or Social Media.

Weitzman and Greenberg (2002) in their book '*Learning Language and Loving It*' state, "For a child, being face-to-face with you adds a special quality to the interaction. It brings you closer to her, physically and emotionally, and makes her feel that you're really with her" (Weitzman & Greenberg, p.75).

Libbert (2017) in a article revealed that excessive Smartphone and Social Media is distancing modern mothers from their children to this extent that they are unable to spend time with their children and help their children with their homework and extra-curricular activities. Not only this by setting wrong examples of excessive Social Media usage mothers were reported to be passing on social media and Smartphone addiction to their children.

Cohen (2009) in a article reported a case of a woman parent who due to addiction to Facebook was not able to give quality time to her daughter; the parent was found to be so badly addicted to chatting and posting on Facebook that she would often ignore her daughter and the persistent requests for the help her daughter required in homework (see para 1-2).

Taylor (2013) in his article states that where on the one hand children's engagement with their Smartphones and Social Networking Sites have provided them with more independence from the involvement and intrusion of their parents in their social lives, on the other hand parents perceive the Smartphone and Social Networking Site obsession of their children as a cause of weak communication and loss of control over their children's activities (see para 5).

Kirik et al. (2015) in their study state that children are found to be addicted to social media primarily when their parents due to lack of knowledge fail to guide them on the constructive and positive use of Social Media (see p.121). Negligence of parents towards their children often works as a push factor for the children to use Social Media and this can badly affect parent-child relationship.

Turkle (2012) in her book "*Alone Together: Why We Expect More from Technology and Less From Each Other*" found that children felt very bad when their parents valued them over Social Media, Smartphones. Children were found to be the sufferers and they complained the most about their parents giving more time to Smartphones and Social Media, parents were found to be excessively using Smartphones while narrating bedtime stories to their children and during meal eating hours, at sport events and in the car.

A study by Chen, Goh and Li (2010) found that even though Facebook allows parents to be frequently updated of their child's online and offline activities, in some cases it might hamper parent-child relationship. This study found that in some cases the desire of parents to stay updated about their child's life would not only make them frequently use Facebook but it was also found that excessive Facebook usage by parents can make them indulge in the surveillance of their child's Facebook wall; this surveillance of Facebook wall by parents often hampers the child's privacy and causes problems in the parent-child relationship wherein children see their parents as intruders harming their privacy (p.12). It was also found that parents' surveillance of their child's Facebook wall can even make them impose parental authority; negative comments by the parents on Facebook wall are often deleted by their children and this could harm parent-child relationship (p.7).

Manickam (2013) Parents reported that Facebook caused changes in the behavior and characteristics of the children themselves. Facebook addiction is greater among children who come from families where both parents are working. Facebook posed potential threat from dangerous predators to the children who desired for love, affection, and companionship. It can be understood from this study that children took to Facebook addiction when they felt lonely at home due to the absence of their parents.

Zebron, Sigauke and Musingafi (2013) in their study aimed at examining the impact of the Facebook on child-parent bonding and parental authority over their children's activities in Zimbabwe. Their study established that parents have become strangers to their children, bonding has been lost, household chores are ignored and most basic norms and values have been neutralized by the Facebook culture that has developed among children and adolescents. Parental control of what children should learn and do has been overtaken by the Facebook. The study recommended that access to Facebook should be under parental supervision. For bonding well with their adolescent children, parents must go by appropriate parenting styles taking into consideration the sensitivity of adolescents.

Wolak et al. (2003) in their study found that adolescents who had a conflicting relationship with their parents due to lack of good or low communication level were more inclined to form online friendships on Social Media.

Bhola and Mahakud (2014) in their study found that adolescents (18-20 years) used Social Networking Sites for making new friends, they ignored daily activities for texting, chatting. Social Networking Sites were used in solitude to maintain secrecy and hide things from parents. Adolescents reported frustration in the absence of Social Networking Sites. With the help of this study it is quite clear that Social Media makes children hide things from their parents which signifies weak parent-child relationship due to the negative impact of Social Media.

Coyne et al. (2014) in their study found that excessive or high usage of Social Networking Sites by adolescents without the control of their parents and without their parents being friends with them can weak parent-child relationships and bring negative outcomes for adolescents like aggression and delinquency.

4.10 Impact of Social Media Addiction on the Romantic Relationships

Clayton, Nagurney and Smith (2013) conducted a study on 205 Facebook users from the age group 18-82 to examine if excessive Facebook usage increased negative interpersonal relationship outcomes like physical cheating, emotional cheating and break up or divorce. The results of the study found that excessive Facebook usage often increases conflict between romantic partners which further yields negative relationship outcomes like emotional and physical cheating; in worst cases it often leads to break-ups and divorce.

Elphinston and Noller (2011) in their study based on undergraduates found that high level of Facebook usage can negatively affect romantic relationships. They found that excessive Facebook usage by a user involved in a romantic relationship increases the surveillance behavior of a user towards their romantic partner which leads to romantic jealousy further proliferating romantic dissatisfaction.

Clayton (2014) conducted a study on the sample of 581 Twitter users from the age group 18-67 years. His study found that active and excessive Twitter use often leads to negative romantic relationship outcomes irrespective of the length of the romantic relationship. The study suggested that active Twitter usage increases Twitter conflict between romantic partners' further increasing breakup, divorce and infidelity.

Farrugia (2013) in a study titled, '*Facebook and relationships: A Study of How Social Media Use Is Affecting Long Term Relationships*', conducted an online survey where a sample of 255 respondents was generated using convenience and snowball sampling. Convenience sampling was used for participants who were studying for various graduate programs at Rochester Institute of Technology and for the ones who were Researcher's friend at Facebook. Snowball sampling was employed for Facebook users who shared the online survey link to their friends. The final sample was of 181 female respondents, 71 male respondents, and three respondents who failed to answer. Researcher aimed at studying four elements of relationship satisfaction, Facebook usage, surveillance and jealousy via their questions in the online survey. Results revealed a connection between stage of relationship and relationship satisfaction when Facebook was being used and specifically in case of blooming relationships which

were formed via Facebook the importance of Facebook increased. It was found that during initial stage of relationship when self-disclosure increased then surveillance increased via Facebook but when relationship matured or bloomed to its fullness then Facebook usage decreased with time. It was found that if one partner from a couple uses Facebook chronically and reveals too much personal information then it can lead to jealousy. For couples being affected by jealousy decreasing the usage of Facebook was suggested.

Marshall (2012) in her study found that excessive exposure of the users to Facebook particularly the Facebook profiles of their ex-romantic partners can negatively hamper their personal growth and post breakup recovery. The study found that Facebook users who didn't unfriend their ex-romantic partners reported less negative feelings, longing and sexual desire for their ex-romantic partner but at the same time Facebook exposure negatively obstructed such users from moving on from the memories of their past romantic relationship and this hampered the personal growth of the users by inhibiting the process of healing.

Ridgway and Clayton (2016) in their study found that excessive monitoring of Instagram selfie-posts of one's romantic partner could lead to verbal disputes and cause Instagram-fuelled conflict between romantic partners. Though on one hand selfie posting could increase body image satisfaction, on the other hand 'Likes and comments' received by a selfie-post on Instagram could also fuel jealousy and make a romantic partner jealous. The results of the study indicate that the popularity of one's Instagram selfie posts could make a user indulge in the development of an online relationship with other Instagram users which could increase infidelity and dissolution of relationships. Researchers suggest that marriage counselors must not limit themselves to inquiring couples about their offline problems but focus primarily on inquiring online behavior like selfie-posting and engagement with other online users which causes their romantic partners to get jealous of their behavior (see p. 6).

Muise, Christofides, and Desmarais (2009) in their study found that Facebook exposes 'users' to excessive information which has potential to provoke jealousy in them for their romantic partner. There results of the study indicate that the increased jealousy leads to increase in users surveillance of the Facebook profile of their romantic partner particularly posts shared. The study found that many users reported addiction to Social Media and admitted that they addictively indulged in the surveillance of their romantic partner's profile. Facebook brings out more jealousy among its users when they come across the pictures or posts of their romantic partners with their ex-romantic partners or unknown individuals. This jealousy is further heightened if Facebook users realize that their romantic partners have not unfriended their ex-romantic partners.

Utz, Muscanell, and Khalid (2015) in their study found that even though Snapchat was used for finding, flirting and engaging with new romantic partners, Snapchat provoked more jealousy among users engaged in romantic relationships. It is interesting to note here that both Facebook and Snapchat have potential to pose threats to the romantic relationships but according to this study it is Snapchat which poses more threat than Facebook.

5. DISCUSSION

Relevant literature has revealed that although there is a lot of published literature on the impact of Internet on Social Relationships yet very few empirical research studies exist on the social media addiction and impact of excessive usage of Social Media on parent-child relationships or romantic relationships. On the basis of reviewed literature we can infer that Social Media and Social Networking Sites in particular have a negative impact on the parent-child relationships and romantic relationships. When it comes to parent-child relationships it can be inferred that both parents and children experience loss of physical connection marked by negligence and neglect towards each other's well-being; both parents and children reported communication gap and behavioral addiction problems due to excessive Social Media usage. When it comes to romantic relationships it can be inferred that excessive Social Media usage by the Social Media Users makes them indulge in the surveillance or excessive monitoring of their romantic partner's posts on Social Networking Sites like Snapchat, Instagram and Facebook; the surveillance arouses jealousy among the Social Media users for their romantic partners specifically when they realize that their romantic partners are communicating with other online users like ex-romantic partners; jealousy further arouses Social Media users to develop conflicts with their romantic partners and finally conflicts often lead to break-up or separation in romantic relationships.

6. SOLUTIONS: PREVENTING AND OVERCOMING SOCIAL MEDIA ADDICTION FOR HEALTHY RELATIONSHIPS

Romantic partners addicted to Social Media must try replacing the activity of Social Media usage with some other activities like going on an adventurous trip together, cooking together without the intrusion of Smartphone or Social Media in their personal space and communication. If necessary then romantic partners must take help of a counselor.

Parents must keep a strict check on their children by limiting their Social Media usage time. It is also important for parents to understand that they cannot command their child unless they themselves set an ideal of using Social Media in limit. It is important for parents to understand that excessive Social Media usage by their child could be the result of the loneliness experienced by the child so rather than blaming the child parents must inquire their child in a friendly manner. Parents must make sure that their child gets involved in extra-curricular activities so that there is less time left for Social Media. Parents must take help of a counselor if they feel things go out of hand.

7. CONCLUSION

Social Media Addiction is a contemporary social problem affecting human relationships. In this paper an attempt was made to study the impact of social media addiction on two specific relationships, parent-child relationships and romantic relationships. The paper relied on secondary data and relevant sources of literature have been reviewed, including research papers from journals, books, newspaper articles, magazines and e-articles. The paper highlighted that outcomes of Social Media Addiction can be compared to any other form of substance addiction considering its negative impact on the functioning of parent-child relationships and romantic relationships. On the basis of inferences drawn from the review of literature it can be concluded that it is the need of an hour to empirically study the phenomenon of Social Media Addiction and to explore the possible functional threats posed by it to human relationships and responsibilities.

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